

1. linguistic interpretation, main task and main technique, incomprehensible, rare use, old, special words and expressions, grammar phenomena and other similar language facts, a dictionary or linear explanation (the main purpose of the analysis.;

2) Lingo-O-StylisticThe analysis is the metaphorical tools of a literary text, the aesthetic effect given by syntheses (the main technique here is the search for a synthesizing principle in the speech representation tool);

Comprehensive linguistic analysis. The main method of this analysis is to examine the text by defining the figurative poetic structure of the text with the message of the text and the figurative language tools system.

He cannot determine the form, the ideological intentions of the writing, the characteristics of the species, and the aesthetic functions. Analysis defines the functional role and forms of language units in the speech: the suitability of the choice of words, the conversions of speech, grammar forms, unique use of language in the literary text and a philosophical linguistic text analysisBranches such as philosophical branches such as philosophical branches, such as model, seem to be a compelling need. Today, linguistic analysis, analysis of a literary text - examination of a text is considered a historical fact of social thought development - a historical truth - and a stylistic text- Investigation of use techniques.

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